

SECURITY ISSUES IN THE HOTEL SYSTEM: A CASE OF CHINESE HOTEL INDUSTRY

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Abstract. In this article, the legislative framework of the People's Republic of China focused on security issues in the hotel system and using the country's experiences in the field of tourism will be included recommendations to increase the security level of hotels in Uzbekistan. The implementation of a medical staff in hotels is the basis of ensuring the medical safety of guests.

INTRODUCTION

In the tourism industry, the availability of touristic resources and infrastructure, as well as the safety of existing infrastructures, are one of the issues that are of constant importance for the development of tourist flow. If it is deemed that the touristic infrastructure is a set of services aimed at meeting the daily needs of the tourist, apartment-providing is an significant need for every tourist who are visiting a tourist destination.

Hotel security is a strategy of measurements which are targeted at managing the safety and security of guests in and around the hotel, which in turn includes personal, property and vehicle security of guests and security procedures, systems and personnel in the rooms. At this point, it should be said that in today's modern society, hotels that offer services to domestic and international tourists as accommodation with certain standards have had their own characteristics in every era. In the past centuries, hotels were called “karvonsaroy” in eastern countries which means to say somewhere is possible to stop and sleep, and their importance in society was related to overnight stays. 21st century hotels can offer not only overnight stays, but almost all services that make visitors feel the atmosphere of a personal home. For an instance, these services include car rental, spa, helipad, golf course, casino, hotel beaches and resort facilities. However, it is not seemed sufficient for state-of-the-art hotels in the era of globalization processes. Because, regardless of whether hotels have all kinds of amenities, the fact that the guests' safety is ensured to leave a

reliable brand impression on the customers mind regarding to this hotel where safety and security system can be applicable.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The hotel business as a service sector is an essential part of the tourism industry, which differs from other types of industries such as manufacturing and agriculture. As well, the safety and security system in hotels is considered as a key point of attracting touristic flow in the touristic destinations.

Lashley notes how the focus of service delivery and how it is received are based on first impressions by the customer. These are often described as ‘moments of truth’ where there is the emotional management of labour to ensure that the customer obtains a quality product and the highest level of service delivery. [1]

According to Darrell Clifton, “While it is hard enough to protect a nuclear power plant from intruders, terrorists, thieves, and spies, it is even more difficult to keep those same persons out of a hotel that is open to the public. Many of the traditional methods of security, such as locks, alarms, and cameras, are still used at our facilities, but we also have to employ more creative methods, such as patrol, behavioral recognition, and passive deterrence (signs, reminders, and awareness)”. [2]

Lebe and Vrecko say that many consumers prefer if the company has responsibility; it will help company get more consumer loyalty (2014). [3]

RESULTS

The most visited countries in the world have always paid special attention to the safety of tourists. At the same time, China is one of the largest tourism investment markets, while the hospitality industry is a rapidly developing economy, and this industry is once again becoming one of the most important economic pillars of the country. The People's Republic of China is one of the countries that implement legal and practical reforms to make tourists feel safe in hotels. In China, which is a leader among developed countries, you can find 5-star hotels with unusual shapes, from ten-dollar capsules. The Chinese government will take legal measures to regulate the activities of star hotels that show such a high rating and are recognized by world tourists as safe hotels. The government has taken a serious series of actions to boost hotel safety and security measures in this country, including strict rules and standards for hotel construction and operation. For example, every night Chinese hotels are required to report about foreigners staying in their hotels to the local public security office. This is done in order to ensure national and international security of the country.

By the end of 2022, there were about 279,000 hotels and about 14.3 million accommodations in China. Almost 19,600 of these hotels are located in China's four major cities: Beijing, Shanghai, Guangzhou and Shengzan. [4]

Figure. 1 Tourist visits to the People's Republic of China (by year)

Source: World Tourism Barometer – Volume – 21 Issue 2 – May 2023 data.

It is clear that before the pandemic, China as a touristic destination received more than 65 thousand tourists and received 254.6 billion dollars from tourism. Since 2020, due to the decrease in the flow of tourists, the indicators of the export volume of tourism have also started to decrease. It is known that Covid-19 has had a significant negative impact on the growth of tourism in the economy of a developed country like China. Despite this, today the People's Republic of China has significantly recovered its tourism potential. According to the information provided by the Ministry of Tourism and Culture, 119 million local tourists traveled around the country as part of the 3-day Qing Ming Festival, which is widely celebrated as a traditional spring holiday in China. [5] Using China's experience in tourism security, which has shown rapid growth in tourism, and establishing international cooperation can be useful for Uzbekistan's national model of tourism development.

Beijing City Government Summit No. 54, Beijing People's Government Resolution No. 178 Review of the "Hotel Security Law" to strictly establish security measurements in hotels and contained a number of articles on taking valuable measures in case of violations of the established laws. [6]

Personnel training issues are also important according to the law so that customers do not get food poisoning in hotels. In case of violations of the provisions specified in this Law, the Tourism Administration, as the responsible organization, will apply administrative penalties in accordance with the provisions.

DISCUSSION

There are several dangers that threaten the safety of tourists in hotels, and to avoid them, tourists are required to be aware in hotels. As well, hotels play a crucial role in ensuring the safety of guests by implementing appropriate measures to mitigate possible threats and risks in hotels.

Table 1. Several threats which are encountered by tourists in hotels.

r	Threats	Description	Solutions
.	Criminal cases	This includes theft, robbery, assault or other criminal activity on or around the hotel premises.	Security measures such as surveillance cameras and security guards are installed in the hotels.
.	Sanitation problems	Tourists may face health risks related to poor sanitation, food, infectious diseases, bed bugs or other hygiene problems in the hotel environment.	Hotels are responsible for cleanliness and implementing appropriate hygiene protocols to prevent the spread of infectious diseases.
.	Natural disasters	Hotels located in areas prone to natural disasters such as earthquakes, hurricanes, floods or forest fires may pose a threat to the safety of tourists.	Hotels should have emergency preparedness plans for the evacuation of guests and the provision of emergency care and emergency medical assistance during such events.
	Fire hazard	Faulty electrical	Hotels must comply

•		wiring, inadequate fire safety measures and fire hazards pose a threat to guest safety in hotels.	with fire safety regulations, conduct regular inspections, and train employees and guests on safety from fire.
•	Terrorist acts	Tourists may face the threat of terrorist attacks or acts of violence targeting hotels and tourist destinations.	Implementing security measures such as screening processes and emergency response protocols such as biometric verification to protect guests from terrorist threats can be an effective response to the threat.
•	Cyber safety	As technology and the use of online booking platforms develop, tourists may face fraud such as data breaches and identity theft when using hotel services or accessing Wi-Fi networks.	Hotels are encouraged to invest in cybersecurity measures to protect guest privacy and facilitate secure transfers and ensure security.

Taking into account the above-mentioned risks, the hotel association pays great attention to security issues, as well as creating sufficient conditions for the relaxation and recreation of visiting international and domestic tourists. However, in the Internet era, it is considered appropriate to increase security measurements. In particular, it is important for tourists to be aware of the risks that are likely to occur and take precautions to protect themselves while staying in hotels.

CONCLUSION

Paying special attention to security issues in the hotel system in Uzbekistan by studying the legal framework of the People's Republic of China, which has a unique tourism model in the tourism industry and has been able to attract humanity for centuries with the “Great Wall of China” is becoming an important part of the period. At this point, it is permissible to create the position of a medical worker in hotels in order to strengthen security measures in hotels of Uzbekistan. The presence of an emergency medical personnel in the hotel significantly reduces the risk level when customers feel symptoms of illness, when an existing disease in the body attacks,

food poisoning and similar situations are observed. In order to create hotels that meet world standards, the following are recommended:

- formulation and implementation of hotel services organization requirements;
- ensuring that hotel employees are trained in professional development courses every three years (especially chefs, waiter/waitress and restaurant employees);
- regulating necessary conditions for providing medical services in hotels;
- to consider the issues of applying strict measures and bringing administrative responsibility in cases where hotel services are not properly organized.

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